

FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF CFRP SPECIMEN AFTER LIGHTNING TEST

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SUMMARY

This paper examines the basic fracture behavior of CFRP laminate after lightning strikes. The relationship between the fracture behavior and applied lightning parameters was examined by performing a damage inspection using non-destructive tests (NDTs). Residual compressive strength was investigated by performing compressive tests and comparative study with conventional CAI tests.

Keywords: CFRP, Lightning strike, NDT, Residual strength

INTRODUCTION

At present, because of their potential for reducing weight, the widespread use of CFRP laminated composites in the principal structures of new-generation commercial aircraft is being planned. Although these advanced composites have superior mechanical properties to conventional aluminum alloy, they usually show large strength degradation due to internal damage such as delamination and matrix cracks. One of the major causes of internal damage is impact through tool dropping and fragment hits during manufacturing, maintenance or operation. Lightning strikes are another possible cause of internal damage to laminated composite structures [1]. Internal damage caused by impact has been investigated by a number of researchers, and detailed fracture mechanisms have been clarified [2–5]. The direct effect of lightning strikes on laminated composite structures and their fracture behavior have also been investigated [6,7], and on the basis of the investigation results, lightning protection systems for direct and indirect effects have been proposed [8]. However, it is difficult to prevent damage completely, even if the appropriate lightning protection systems are applied to the composite structure. Furthermore, a strength degradation of composite structures resulting from lightning damage has attracted little attention.

In this study, therefore, to investigate the fundamental fracture behaviour of CFRP laminate damaged by lightning strikes and their residual strength characteristics, residual compressive strength tests are performed on the CFRP specimens with no lightning protection system following artificial lightning strike tests which simulate natural lightning stroke. The damage caused by lightning tests is inspected using non-destructive inspection (NDI) techniques and the results compared with the results of an inspection of impact damage. For comparison of residual strength characteristics

between lightning damage and impact damage, conventional compression after impact (CAI) tests are also performed. The relationships between internal delamination areas and residual strength, and differences in stress-strain relationships between post-lightning specimens and post-impact specimens, are discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Materials and Specimens

The material used in this study was a graphite/epoxy laminate made of toughened epoxy resin #133 and middle-modulus/high-strength IM600 graphite fiber produced by Toho Tenax. IM600/133 has been developed for aerospace usage and has high compression-after-impact (CAI) strength. The composite was processed by prepreg molding in an autoclave following a recommended cure cycle. The sizes of the specimens were selected as 150 mm × 100 mm with reference to ASTM D7137 [9]; the residual strength test standard for polymer matrix composites. The specimens were cut out from the quasi-isotropic parent laminates in dimensions of 350 mm × 350 mm. The specimens had a quasi-isotropic stacking sequence $[45/0/-45/90]_{4s}$ and were approximately 4.7 mm thick.

Lightning Test

In order to simulate natural lightning strikes, an impulse high-current generator (ICG) produced by Haefely Test AG. (Fig. 1 a)) was used in this study. Figure 1 b) schematically shows the circuit of the generators, where R_s and R_o are resistances and C_s is capacitance. By varying R_s , R_o , and C_s , an arbitrary waveform can be generated. A DC current transformer (DCCT) was connected to the ground wire from the specimen, and the waveform of the applied impulse current was measured using an oscilloscope. A detailed description of the lightning test equipment and setup used can be found in [10]. The specimens were placed on a test jig, comprised mainly of two 15-mm-thick GFRP laminates and a metal discharge probe. The lower GFRP laminate supported the specimen and the upper laminate held the probe. The upper GFRP laminate was supported by four GFRP threaded rods so that the distance between the laminates could be adjusted with screws. The distance between the tip of the discharge probe and specimen surface was adjusted to 2.0 mm. To ensure an earth ground connection with the specimens, a copper sheet connected to the earth ground was inserted between the specimens and the lower GFRP laminate.

The tested impulse waveform conditions are listed in Table 1. Systematic experimental conditions were examined so that when a CFRP laminate comes into contact with an impulse current waveform, responses can be understood and characterized. Usually, natural lightning displays complicated time series variation in current waveforms. To simplify matters, the lightning environment was synthesized from negative and positive natural lightning characteristics into components designated A, B, C, and D. A natural lightning environment and descriptions of the standard lightning environment for aircraft design are described in a committee report by the SAE [11].

In this study, for component A of a positive first return stroke, three types of waveform with differing duration times were tested, as listed in Table 1. The impulse waveforms

are defined with a pair of numbers: the first number represents the time to peak and the latter represents the time to half the value. The detailed definition of waveform is shown in Fig. 2. The action integrals shown in Table 1 represent the t specific energy of the impulse current, as follows:

$$AI = \int i^2 dt \tag{1}$$

where i is the time-varying electrical current of lightning waveforms.

Internal damage inspection for the in-plane direction of the post-lightning test specimens was performed using an ultrasonic flaw detector (Gnes Corporation) with a 5 Mz probe. For the thickness direction, damage inspection using micro X-ray CT scanning was performed.

a) Impulse current generator (ICG)

b) Test circuit

Figure 1 Lightning test setup.

Figure 2 Lightning waveform definition.

Table 1 Lightning test conditions.

	Waveform [μ s]	Peak Current [kA]	Electrical Charge [C]	Action Integral [A ² s]
I		20	0.20	2831.38
II	2.6/10.5	30	0.31	6273.28
III		40	0.41	11440.90
IV		20	0.42	5444.82
V	4/20	30	0.63	12350.97
VI		40	0.82	20887.35

Residual Compression Strength Test

Compression strength tests were performed with reference to ASTM D7137 for the post-lightning test specimens. Prior to compressive tests, back-to-back strain gauges were attached to the specimen surfaces far from the damaged area. Compressive loadings were applied using a mechanically driven machine, Instron 5589, at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. The compressive test apparatus is shown in Fig. 3 a). For a comparison, a conventional compression after impact (CAI) test was also performed [12]. The specimen was subjected to impact test, ultrasonic inspection, and compressive test. The impact test was performed using a weight-drop type machine, Instron Dynatup 9250, with a hemispherical impactor (diameter: 15.9 mm). The applied impact energy was set at 3.32, 6.7, 9.63, 7.56, 8.13 J/mm. Damage inspection of the post-impact specimens was performed using an ultrasonic flaw detector as with the damaged specimen after lightning tests.

a) Compressive testing setup

b) Weight-drop testing machine

Figure 3 Residual compression strength test apparatus (ASTM D7137).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Lightning Tests

Artificial lightning tests were performed with the test conditions listed in Table 1. The post-lightning test specimens showed carbon fiber breakage in the vicinity of the lightning attachment point several layers deep from the surface. Fiber dissipation and resin vaporization can also be observed in a region roughly 20 mm in diameter. At the same time, a strip-shaped ply-lift in the fiber direction of the outermost 45-degree layer is observed. The ply-lift initiation point is the lightning attachment point, the width being almost the same as the diameter of the surface fiber damaged region. Outside the surface fiber damage region, a resin deterioration area is observed. The visual appearance of the tested specimen with condition VI (4/20 μ s with peak current of 40.0 kA) is shown in Fig. 4, a typical result for an artificial lightning test. Fig. 4 (a) shows the overhead view, and Fig. 4 (b) shows a magnified view of lightning strike attachment point. Typical ultrasonic C-scan image of the post-lightning test specimen is shown in Fig. 5 (a). The results show that the lightning tests created large delaminations; the delamination propagates in the shape of a pair of fans along the fiber direction starting from the lightning attachment point in each interlayer. Focusing on the B-scope result, it can be observed that the internal damage area is limited to the vicinity of the damaged surface in the direction of thickness. For a comparison, a typical UT scan results for post-impact specimen is shown in Fig. 5 (b). Comparing these with the results of the lightning test, it can be clearly seen that both damage propagations in the in-plane direction are quite similar: delamination in both the lightning test and the drop weight test propagate in the shape of a pair of fans in each interlayer. However, looking at the direction of thickness, though the internal damage area due to lightning strikes is limited to the vicinity of damaged surface as previously described, the internal damage due to impact propagates across the entire thickness of the specimen.

The measured maximum damaged depth and the measured delamination area show a positive dependence on the applied specific energy (action integral) of the impulse current (Fig. 6 a), b)). The product of the applied action integral and the electrical resistance of the target material is the generated Joule heat. This is the resistive heating due to the applied impulse current and the relatively high electrical resistance of the material, which results in the delamination of the CFRP laminate. Subsequent burning or pyrolysis of the resin around graphite fibers would result in delamination propagation inside the laminate. It is conjectured that the relatively large scatter of the results is due to the instability of the progress of damage caused by rapid evaporation of the resin. However, when focusing on the waveform variation of applied artificial lightning, it is shown that the waveform has little effect on the damage response for each damage mode under the experimental conditions attempted in this study.

a) Overhead view of damaged specimen

b) Magnified view of lightning attachment point

Figure 4 Specimen after artificial lightning strike
(condition VI: 4/20 μ s, 40 kA, t = 4.7 mm)

a) Lightning damage

b) Drop weight damage

Figure 5 Ultrasonic C-scan result

a) Maximum damaged depth

b) Delamination area

Figure 6 Relationship between damage size and action integral

RESIDUAL STRENGTH

The obtained residual compression strength for post-lightning test specimens and CAI strength are plotted against the measured delamination area in Fig. 7. Although there are differences of cause of damage, lightning test and impact, and damage distribution in the thickness direction, obtained residual strengths show a linear relationship with the total delamination area which represents the summation of all delamination in each inter-lamina created inside the same specimen

On the other hand, there is a difference between the post-lightning specimen and the post-impact specimens on stress-strain response. Typical stress-strain relationships for the compression strength test for the post-lightning test and the CAI test are shown in Fig. 8 (a) and (b) respectively. The strain-stress relationship between the impact side and the opposite side is almost identical in the CAI test. The measured strain increased linearly with increases in the applied load. This fact suggests to us that initiation of delamination progress and catastrophic failure occur almost simultaneously because of the high inter-lamina toughness of the tested material. The stress-strain response of residual strength test for the post-lightning specimen shows a large difference between the lightning attachment side and the opposite side. Unlike the CAI test results, it was observed that delamination grew orthogonally to the loading direction with increases in the applied load. This indicates that there is the possibility of an existing resin deteriorated area having decreased inter-lamina toughness due to resistive heating effects outside the delamination area inspected using ultrasonic C-scan and micro X-ray CT scan. The differences in delamination progress behaviours between post-impact and post-lightning test specimens should be further investigated.

However, under the experimental conditions in this study, it is confirmed that residual strength can be expected from the total delamination area regardless of the cause of damage: conventional impact or lightning test.

Figure 7 Relationship between total delamination area and residual compressive strength

a) compressive test for post-lightning test

b) CAI test

Figure 8 Stress-strain curve of residual strength test

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this study, experimental investigations into the fundamental damage behaviour and the residual strength characteristics of damaged CFRP specimens after artificial lightning tests were performed. Systematic experimental conditions were used during the tests in order to understand the relationship between lightning parameters and damage response or residual strength. A comparative study on damage inspection and residual strength using post-lightning specimen and post-impact specimen (CAI) were also performed. Resulting delamination areas and maximum damaged depths from the lightning test were governed by the action integral of applied impulse current. The damage progress in the in-plane direction of lightning damage was similar to that of impact damage, whereas the damage distributions in the thickness direction were quite different to one another. However, it was confirmed that residual compressive strengths can be determined by the total delamination area despite the difference in cause of damage.

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